

Benchmarking 31 Large Language Models on the AMD BC-250:

An Empirical Study of Vulkan-Based Inference on a Unified Memory APU

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Abstract—The AMD BC-250 is a repurposed cryptocurrency mining board with a Cyan Skillfish APU (Zen 2 CPU, GFX1013 GPU, 24 CUs) and 16 GB of unified GDDR6 memory. Because AMD’s ROCm libraries do not support GFX1013, Vulkan via the Mesa RADV driver was the only GPU compute path verified as functional in this work. This study documents the Linux kernel tuning (`ttm.pages_limit`) that enables access to the full 16 GB for inference, and reports benchmark results for 31 large language models (3B–35B parameters) covering generation speed, filled-context scaling with real-token payloads, output quality across five task types, and cold-start latency. A 35-billion-parameter Mixture-of-Experts model with 3B active parameters reaches 37.5 tok/s. Of the 31 models tested, 24 reach a verified 64K filled-context ceiling. Silent context truncation by the Ollama runtime is documented and shown to affect benchmark validity. As a supplementary evaluation, the same Vulkan path is also used for image generation, vision inference, and video generation, though these modalities were tested with less rigour.

Keywords: AMD APU, Benchmark methodology, Edge AI, Large language models, Mixture of Experts, Unified memory architecture, Vulkan inference

I. INTRODUCTION

Running large language models locally, without relying on cloud services, is increasingly relevant for cost, privacy, and latency reasons, but it requires hardware with sufficient GPU memory and a compatible compute framework [1], [2]. Datacenter-class GPUs with 24–80 GB of dedicated VRAM satisfy these requirements readily; low-cost consumer and embedded hardware generally does not.

This study evaluates the AMD BC-250, a decommissioned cryptocurrency mining board, as a platform for local AI inference. The board integrates a Zen 2 CPU (6 cores, 12 threads) with a GFX1013 GPU (24 CUs, 1536 SPs) and 16 GB of GDDR6 in a Unified Memory Architecture (UMA). GFX1013 occupies an intermediate position in AMD’s product line (GFX10.1-era silicon incorporating select RDNA 2 features), commonly referred to as “RDNA 1.5” by the developer community [3], [4]. As decommissioned mining hardware, these boards are available at a fraction of the cost of discrete GPUs with comparable memory capacity.

The principal constraint is software support: neither AMD’s ROCm stack nor OpenCL via Mesa’s rusticl was found to be functional on GFX1013 (Section III-B). Vulkan through

the Mesa RADV driver [5] was the only GPU compute path verified as functional in the tested configuration (Fedora 43, Mesa 25.3.4, kernel 6.18.9), and even this required resolving kernel memory limits before models exceeding 7B parameters could run.

The paper reports four sets of results:

- 1) It documents the kernel-level configuration (`ttm.pages_limit`) required to make the full 16 GB available for GPU allocation on this hardware.
- 2) It presents benchmark results for 31 LLM models (3B–35B parameters) with statistical validation ($CV < 1.5\%$), filled-context scaling using 80% real-token payloads, quality assessment across five task types, and cold-start latency measurements.
- 3) It reports on silent context truncation in the Ollama runtime, a behaviour that affects benchmark validity regardless of hardware.
- 4) As a supplementary evaluation, it tests image generation, multimodal vision inference, and video generation on the same Vulkan compute path; these results use single runs and carry less statistical weight than the LLM benchmarks.

II. RELATED WORK

The majority of published LLM inference research targets discrete GPUs with dedicated VRAM. The llama.cpp project [6] enabled quantised GGUF model execution on CPUs and mixed CPU/GPU configurations; Ollama [7] provides an HTTP API layer above it. Published benchmarks overwhelmingly focus on NVIDIA/CUDA or AMD/ROCm hardware [8]; Vulkan-only inference platforms appear relatively underrepresented in the literature.

Recent Unified Memory Architectures, most notably Apple Silicon, have shown that shared CPU–GPU memory pools can sustain practical LLM inference throughput [9]. The BC-250’s UMA is analogous in concept but differs in implementation: GDDR6 rather than LPDDR5, no dedicated matrix accelerator units, and Vulkan rather than Metal as the compute API.

Post-training quantisation techniques (GPTQ [10], AWQ [11], GGUF IQ2 variants) can compress models by 4–8× with acceptable quality degradation; however, the combination of extreme quantisation (2.5 bits/weight) with Vulkan inference

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on non-standard GPU silicon has not, to the best of the author’s knowledge, been examined in prior work.

Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) architectures [12] activate only a subset of their parameters per token. On hardware lacking dedicated matrix cores, where all computation is dispatched through scalar ALUs, the throughput advantage of sparse activation is expected to be pronounced. This study provides empirical observations relevant to that point.

The models benchmarked here span several families: Qwen 2.5 [13], Qwen 3 [14], Qwen 3.5 [15], Llama 3 [16], Gemma 2 and Gemma 3 [17], Phi-4 [18], and DeepSeek-R1 [19]. Image generation pipelines build on latent diffusion models [20].

III. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE STACK

A. AMD BC-250 Specifications

The BC-250 board uses an AMD Cyan Skillfish APU (Table I). The CPU and GPU share a single 16 GB GDDR6 pool through a 256-bit bus. The BIOS reserves 512 MB as a framebuffer; the remainder is allocated to the Graphics Translation Table (GTT). In this UMA configuration, “100% GPU offload” means model weights and KV cache reside in GTT pages that the GPU reads directly; there is no PCIe copy.

TABLE I
AMD BC-250 HARDWARE SPECIFICATIONS.

Component	Details
CPU	Zen 2, 6 cores / 12 threads
GPU	Cyan Skillfish (GFX1013) 24 CUs, 1536 SPs
Memory	16 GB GDDR6 unified (256-bit bus)
GTT (tuned)	16 GiB (<code>ttm.pages_limit</code>)
Vulkan total	16.5 GiB (after tuning)
Storage	475 GB NVMe
OS	Fedora 43, kernel 6.18.9
TDP	220 W [21]

The board shipped with a minimal factory BIOS for rack-mount mining. A community-patched BIOS [21] adds standard UEFI features including NVMe boot and fan control.

B. Vulkan as the Sole GPU Compute Path

GFX1013 is listed in LLVM’s AMDGPU target table as supporting `rocm-amdhsa` [4]; however, in the tested configuration, ROCm userspace components were not usable on GFX1013; attempts resulted in a `rocblas_abort()` failure (Table II). OpenCL via Mesa’s `rusticl` also did not work (Mesa 25.3.4, Fedora 43).

In the tested configuration, Vulkan was the only GPU compute path found to be functional. Ollama (version 0.18.0) uses it as the `llama.cpp` backend.

C. Kernel Memory Tuning

Two kernel-level memory limits required adjustment before models above ~ 7 B could run on the GPU.

TABLE II
COMPUTE FRAMEWORK AVAILABILITY ON THE BC-250.

Framework	Status	Notes
amdgpu driver	Works	Auto-detected
Vulkan (RADV)	Works	Mesa 25.3.4
ROCm / HIP	Fails	Not in GPU list
OpenCL (<code>rusticl</code>)	Fails	Not usable

GTT default cap. The `amdgpu` kernel driver defaults to allocating 50% of physical RAM as GTT (≈ 7.4 GiB on a 16 GB system). The legacy fix (`amdgpu.gttsize`) is deprecated in modern kernels [22].

TTM pages_limit. The kernel’s TTM (Translation Table Manager) memory manager independently caps GPU memory allocations at ≈ 7.4 GiB. Without this adjustment, 14B-class models load but produce HTTP 500 errors during inference. Setting `ttm.pages_limit=4194304` (16 GiB in 4 KiB pages) alleviates both limits simultaneously. In the tested environment, this was the only kernel-level change required; the fix was identified empirically and subsequently confirmed via inspection of the TTM source code [23], which exposes `pages_limit` as a writable module parameter.

After tuning, Vulkan reports 16.5 GiB across two logical heaps (8.33 GiB device-local + 8.17 GiB host-visible), backed by the same physical 16 GB.

D. Inference Runtime Configuration

Ollama runs with the following settings:

- `OLLAMA_VULKAN=1` — selects the Vulkan backend.
- `OLLAMA_KV_CACHE_TYPE=q4_0` — quantises the KV cache to 4-bit, reducing KV memory by approximately 4 \times compared to FP16.
- `OLLAMA_CONTEXT_LENGTH=65536` — caps the default context allocation at 64K tokens.
- `OLLAMA_FLASH_ATTENTION=1` — enables flash attention [24].
- `OLLAMA_MAX_LOADED_MODELS=1` — enforces single-model loading to avoid memory contention.
- `OLLAMA_KEEP_ALIVE=30m` — retains the loaded model for 30 minutes; warm-start TTFT stays below 2 s.
- `OOMScoreAdjust=-1000` — protects the Ollama process from the Linux OOM killer.

A 16 GB NVMe swap file serves as a safety net for memory spikes during model loading. In practice, swap usage was 400–850 MB (OS buffers pushed out by model weights), not active paging.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The benchmarks are organised into five phases. All measurements were taken on the same hardware and software stack (Section III), with all background services stopped.

A. Phase 1: Performance Baseline

All 31 models were evaluated with a standardised prompt of approximately 400 tokens (a comparative analysis of

RISC and CISC architectures), with `num_predict=100` and `num_ctx=4096` (4K context window). A single run per model was used, with subsequent statistical validation (Phase 2) confirming the reproducibility of single-run observations on this hardware.

Recorded metrics: generation speed (tok/s), prefill rate (tok/s), time to first token (TTFT), VRAM consumption, GPU offload percentage, number of GPU layers, and NVMe swap delta.

B. Phase 2: Statistical Validation

Eight models spanning the full parameter range (3.2B–35B) were selected for 3-run statistical validation at 4K context. Median, minimum, maximum, and coefficient of variation (CV) of generation speed were computed. Phase 3 context-scaling runs were done in pairs; the mean within-pair CV was 0.55% (max 2.4%).

C. Phase 3: Filled-Context Scaling

1) *Allocation vs. Utilisation*: This phase addresses a methodological distinction that proved important in practice: the difference between context *allocation* and context *utilisation*.

Allocating a large `num_ctx` with a short prompt only tests whether the runtime can reserve KV cache memory. On this hardware, 128K allocation succeeded consistently; filling 128K with real tokens exceeds the 20-minute benchmark timeout for every model tested. Extrapolation from 96K prefill durations (581 s for the MoE, 535 s for qwen3.5:9b) places the 128K TTFT at approximately 17–25 minutes. Within the tested stack and timeout budget, 128K filled-context requests were limited primarily by prefill latency rather than by observed memory exhaustion.

2) *Filled-Context Protocol*: Context was filled to 80% of `num_ctx` with repeated English text blocks (≈ 500 tokens each, drawn from diverse technical domains). For each configuration:

- 1) Target context size: 4K, 8K, 16K, 32K, 64K, 96K, or 128K.
- 2) Prompt constructed by concatenating text blocks until 80% fill.
- 3) Ollama API’s `prompt_eval_count` verified against expected token count. A mismatch indicates *silent truncation*: the runtime processed fewer tokens than submitted without error.
- 4) System RAM and swap monitored via `/proc/meminfo`.
- 5) 20-minute timeout enforced per request.

All 31 models were tested; six core models with 2 runs per configuration, the remainder with 1 run (justified by Phase 2 variance results). Ollama silently truncates some models to their native context limit without error, detectable only by checking `prompt_eval_count`. Confirmed cases: qwen2.5:3b (caps at 32K) and phi4:14b (caps at 16K).

D. Phase 4: Quality Assessment

All 31 models were evaluated on five task types, three runs per task per model (465 trials total). Tasks were designed

as a *practical competence battery*, each probing a distinct, practically relevant capability:

- 1) **Summarisation** — given a 120-word passage, produce exactly three sentences. Scored by keyword presence ($\geq 50\%$) and sentence count.
- 2) **JSON extraction** — given biographical text, return a JSON object with seven specified keys. Scored by valid parse, keys present, values matching.
- 3) **Fact recall** — given five explicit facts, answer a targeted question. Scored by keyword presence.
- 4) **Instruction following** — produce exactly five numbered advantages of solar energy. Scored by regex count.
- 5) **Arithmetic** — compute 17×23 and return only the number. Scored by substring match for “391”.

Scoring was fully automated and deterministic: keyword, JSON-parse, and regex checks executed at test time; no LLM-as-judge or human annotation. The complete task prompts and scoring functions are included verbatim in the benchmark script (`bench-rigorous.py`) in the project repository [25].

By design, these tasks have a high ceiling: a well-functioning 3–4B model should pass most of them. The battery measures *minimum competence preservation under quantisation and hardware constraints*, not peak reasoning ability.

Models ran with `think: false`, though some families ignore this directive and consume the output budget with thinking tokens.

E. Phase 5: Cold-Start Latency

The two primary models were fully unloaded (`ollama stop`), and the time from request submission to first generated token was measured (three runs per model). The Linux page cache was *not* dropped between runs, reflecting realistic conditions where GGUF files remain cached after the first load.

F. Long-Context Quality

To assess whether models can effectively *utilise* information in large contexts (not just generate tokens after a long prompt), two additional test types were run on three models at 16K and 32K:

- **Embedded fact retrieval** — three unique facts planted at 25%, 50%, and 75% positions; the model must retrieve the specific numerical answer.
- **Multi-hop reasoning** — four task types requiring either chaining three scattered arithmetic facts or detecting contradictions between studies separated by thousands of filler tokens.

Two independent runs were conducted per model and context size, yielding 48 multi-hop/synthesis trials.

V. RESULTS

A. Generation Speed and VRAM

Table III shows results for representative models. Every model achieved 100% GPU offload after GTT tuning. One additional model (qwen3:8b at Q8_0) appears in Section V-F

TABLE III
GENERATION SPEED AND VRAM FOR REPRESENTATIVE MODELS AT 4K
CONTEXT. * RECOMMENDED.

Model	Par.	Quant	Gen (t/s)	Pfill (t/s)	VRAM (GiB)	Qual.
llama3.2:3b	3.2B	Q4_K_M	103.8	484.8	2.2	93%
phi4-mini	3.8B	Q4_K_M	87.0	346.3	2.5	93%
gemma3:4b	4B	Q4_K_M	76.5	357.1	3.8	100%
qwen3:8b	8.2B	Q4_K_M	43.1	192.7	5.1	100%
* qwen3.5:9b	9.7B	Q4_K_M	31.7	171.3	7.9	100%
mistral-nemo:12b	12.2B	Q4_0	34.1	159.8	6.7	80%
qwen3:14b	14.8B	Q4_K_M	26.8	108.6	8.9	100%
deepseek-r1:14b	14B	Q4_K_M	28.7	101.4	8.5	100%
* MoE 35B	35/3B	IQ2_M	37.5	127.5	12.3	93%

as a quantisation comparison but is not counted among the 31 distinct models.

Three patterns are visible in the data:

MoE on scalar hardware. The 35B MoE model with only 3B active parameters achieved 37.5 tok/s, faster than the 9.7B dense model (31.7 tok/s) and all 14B dense models (≈ 27 – 29 tok/s), despite its 35 billion total parameters. The most plausible explanation is that MoE models read only 3B worth of weights per token; on hardware lacking matrix accelerators, where throughput appears constrained by memory bandwidth, they approximate the throughput of a 3B model while retaining access to a much larger parameter pool. However, this comparison conflates architecture, model family, and quantisation level, so the hypothesis requires controlled testing to confirm.

Speed scales inversely with parameters. For dense models at the same quantisation, throughput decreases predictably with parameter count: 3B ≈ 87 – 104 tok/s, 8B-class ≈ 43 – 52 tok/s, 14B ≈ 27 – 29 tok/s. This scaling pattern is consistent with memory-bandwidth-limited behaviour as described by [26], since each token requires reading all model weights once from GDDR6, though the hypothesis was not experimentally isolated in this study.

Prefill behaviour. For the two recommended models, prefill converges to approximately 220–230 tok/s in the medium-to-long range, an observed pattern whose mechanism remains unproven and may reflect implementation overhead, memory bandwidth, or both. At very short prompts (< 50 tokens), dispatch overhead dominates and prefill drops to 53–61 tok/s.

B. Statistical Validation

Table IV shows 3-run validation for eight models. CV remains below 1.5% for all tested models. Larger models exhibit tighter variance (0.2%), likely because each token takes longer relative to measurement noise; smaller, faster models show slightly more spread (1.3–1.4%).

The low variance is expected for a UMA system with no PCIe jitter and the CPU governor locked to performance.

C. Context Scaling

1) *Generation Speed Under Filled Context:* Table V shows how generation speed degrades as context utilisation increases.

Fig. 1. Generation speed (tok/s) for all 31 models at 4K context with Q4_0 KV cache. MoE models (hatched) show speed disproportionate to their total parameter count due to sparse activation. Dashed line at 25 tok/s marks interactive-use threshold.

Dense model degradation at 64K ranges from -13% (gemma3:4b) to -75% (phi4-mini). The MoE (-36%) outperforms four of the six dense models but not gemma3:4b (-13%) or qwen3.5:9b (-26%). The MoE’s relatively low degradation is consistent with the expectation [27] that with only 3B active parameters the per-layer attention overhead is proportionally smaller.

During autoregressive decoding, generating each token requires reading all model weights plus the accumulated KV cache from memory. Because the KV cache grows linearly with context length, per-token generation time $t = 1/\text{throughput}$ is expected to increase linearly with n_{ctx} . The measured data are broadly consistent with this prediction: for the MoE model, t increases by a factor of $1.55\times$ between 4K and 64K (a $16\times$ increase in context). The sub-proportional growth suggests that

Fig. 2. VRAM consumption across all benchmarked models. The 16 GiB UMA ceiling (dashed line) is the hard boundary for full GPU offload.

TABLE IV
STATISTICAL VALIDATION: 3 RUNS PER MODEL AT 4K CONTEXT.

Model	Median (tok/s)	Range	CV (%)
qwen3:14b	26.6	26.6–26.7	0.2
mistral-nemo:12b	34.0	33.9–34.0	0.2
qwen3:8b	42.8	42.8–43.0	0.3
MoE 35B-A3B	37.5	37.3–37.6	0.4
qwen3.5:9b	31.7	31.7–31.9	0.4
Qwen3-30B-A3B	58.5	57.9–58.9	0.9
llama3.2:3b	102.2	101.3–103.9	1.3
phi4-mini	86.1	85.0–87.4	1.4

at shorter contexts the fixed cost of reading model weights dominates, and the KV cache contribution becomes significant only at longer contexts. These observations are consistent with a memory-bandwidth-limited regime, though the hypothesis was not isolated experimentally.

2) *Context Ceiling Distribution*: Of the 31 models tested, 24 (77%) reach the 64K filled-context ceiling. Three are limited to 32K due to native model limits (qwen2.5:3b, qwen2.5:7b) or impractical latency (deepseek-r1:14b at 2.3 tok/s). Two are limited by native context windows below 32K: phi4:14b (16K, silent truncation) and gemma2:9b (8K). One model (qwen2.5-coder:7b) pro-

TABLE V
GENERATION SPEED (TOK/S) WITH 80% REAL-TOKEN CONTEXT FILL.
* DENOTES RECOMMENDED MODELS. “—” INDICATES TIMEOUT (>20 MIN) OR SILENT TRUNCATION (†).

Model	4K	16K	32K	64K	Deg.	Ceil.
* MoE 35B	35.4	31.6	27.8	22.9	−36%	64K
* qwen3.5:9b	31.2	29.0	26.8	23.0	−26%	64K
gemma3:4b	74.1	72.2	69.6	64.3	−13%	64K
phi4-mini	74.1	47.1	31.8	18.7	−75%	64K
qwen3:8b	39.4	29.6	22.3	14.3	−64%	64K
qwen3:14b	25.3	20.5	16.4	11.0	−57%	64K
mistral-nemo:12b	31.6	24.1	18.5	12.1	−62%	64K
phi4:14b†	25.7	19.0	—	—	—	16K

Fig. 3. Generation speed degradation with filled context (80% real-token fill). Dense model degradation at 64K ranges from 13% (gemma3:4b) to 75% (phi4-mini); the MoE sits at 36%.

duced a `prompt_eval_count` of zero at all fill levels, suggesting a format incompatibility. One model (qwen3.5-27b) loaded in baseline tests but failed warmup in the filled-context sweep.

3) *KV Cache Quantisation Impact*: Q4_0 KV cache quantisation enables large-context inference on 16 GB UMA. Table VI shows the effect: KV memory drops $\sim 4\times$, pushing the ceiling from 16–24K (FP16) to 128K+ in allocation (though filled context tops out at 64K due to TTFT).

Speed shows no measurable change with KV quantisation

TABLE VI
IMPACT OF KV CACHE QUANTISATION ON CONTEXT CEILING AND SPEED
(QWEN3:14B, Q4_K_M WEIGHTS).

KV Type	14B Ceil.	MoE Ceil.	KV@24K	Gen
FP16 (legacy)	24K	16K	~3.8 GiB	27.2
Q8_0	64K+	64K+	~2.0 GiB	27.3
Q4_0 (deployed)	128K	256K	~1.1 GiB	27.3

TABLE VII
QUALITY TIER DISTRIBUTION ACROSS 31 MODELS (5 TASKS \times 3 RUNS EACH). TWO MODELS LISTED SEPARATELY DUE TO KNOWN LOADING BUGS.

Score	Models	Representative members
100%	15	All 14B, Qwen3 8B family, gemma3:4b/12b, gemma2:9b, qwen3.5:9b
93%	5	MoE 35B-A3B, phi4-mini, llama3.2:3b, llama3.1:8b, glm4:9b
80–87%	3	granite3.3:8b, mistral-nemo:12b, seed-coder-abliterate:8b
73% \leq 40%	2 4	qwen2.5:3b, deepseek-r1:8b Think-token leakage or specialised / broken models
0%	1	qwen3.5-27b (all tasks timed out)
20%	1	qwen2.5:7b (intermittent loading bug)

(27.2–27.3 tok/s at all three levels), suggesting that KV access is not the dominant cost at 24K context.

D. Quality Assessment

1) *Basic Task Quality*: Table VII shows quality across all 31 models. The median score is 100%: 15 models achieved a perfect 15/15, and every recommended model scored \geq 93%.

The MoE model (35B at IQ2_M, \approx 2.5 bits/weight) scored 14/15 (93%); its sole failure was an instruction-following task where it added a preamble before an otherwise correct list. These results suggest that aggressive quantisation can preserve basic task functionality on this hardware.

Failure patterns appear to track model design rather than hardware constraints. Arithmetic ($17 \times 23 = 391$) is the hardest task: five models score 0/3. Fact recall is the easiest: every testable model passes. These appear to be model-level weaknesses rather than BC-250-specific artefacts.

The high median (100%) is expected: the battery was designed to detect *broken* configurations (quantisation failures, loading bugs, think-token leakage), not to rank strong models against each other. Tasks where the ceiling effect is weaker (arithmetic and instruction compliance) do separate models that handle structured output from those that do not. Reasoning depth and generation nuance fall outside the scope of this evaluation.

2) *Long-Context Quality*: Fact retrieval at 16K succeeded without error: 18/18 across three models and three positions (early, middle, late).

Fig. 4. Quality scores across all 31 models. Dashed line at 93% marks the quality threshold. Models sorted by score; recommended models highlighted.

TABLE VIII
LONG-CONTEXT QUALITY: MULTI-HOP REASONING AND SYNTHESIS AT 16K AND 32K FILLED CONTEXT (48 TRIALS).

Task type	Pass/Tot.	Rate	Pattern
Synth.: timeline	12/12	100%	Univ. pass
Synth.: contradict.	11/12	92%	Reliable
Multi-hop: popul.	4/12	33%	Variable
Multi-hop: budget	1/12	8%	Truncation

Multi-hop reasoning proved more challenging (Table VIII). Synthesis tasks (contradictions, timelines) were reliable (23/24 pass). Multi-hop arithmetic, linking three scattered facts, exhibited substantially lower pass rates (5/24), primarily because the 300-token output limit truncated the chain-of-thought reasoning before reaching the final answer.

No model shows a clear advantage: MoE 35B and qwen3.5:9b each scored 10/16, phi4-mini scored 8/16. Results

	(a) 16K Context			(b) 32K Context		
Budget	Fail	Fail	Fail	Fail	Fail	Fail
Population	Pass	Fail	Fail	Pass	Pass	Fail
Contradict.	Pass	Pass	Fail	Pass	Pass	Pass
Timeline	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass	Pass
	3/4	2/4	1/4	3/4	3/4	2/4
	MoE 35B-A3B	qwen3.5 :9b	phi4 -mini	MoE 35B-A3B	qwen3.5 :9b	phi4 -mini

Fig. 5. Long-context quality at 16K and 32K filled context. Synthesis tasks achieve near-perfect scores; multi-hop arithmetic chains show degradation, primarily due to output-length truncation.

TABLE IX
COLD-START TTFT: MODEL FULLY UNLOADED → FIRST GENERATED TOKEN. THREE RUNS PER MODEL.

Model	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Med.	Load
MoE 35B-A3B	18.0 s	18.0 s	17.5 s	18.0 s	16.2 s
qwen3.5:9b	11.9 s	6.8 s	7.0 s	7.0 s	5.6 s

vary between runs (LLM sampling variance), but task-level patterns remain consistent.

E. Cold-Start Latency

The MoE loads from NVMe at ~ 660 MB/s (11 GB GGUF); the 9B model at ~ 1.1 GB/s (6.1 GB GGUF). The qwen3.5:9b Run 1 anomaly (11.9 s vs. 6.8–7.0 s) likely reflects the GGUF file not yet being fully resident in the page cache.

With `OLLAMA_KEEP_ALIVE=30m`, cold start only happens after 30 minutes of idle time. Warm TTFT is 0.3–1.7 s.

F. Quantisation Impact on Speed

Comparing Q4_K_M and Q8_0 on the same model (qwen3:8b) with Q4_0 KV cache (Table X): Q8_0 carries a 67% penalty in weight data volume but is only 28% slower during generation. This non-linear relationship is consistent with Q8_0 requiring simpler dequantisation than the block-scaled Q4_K_M format, while memory transport cost remains the dominant factor on this bandwidth-limited UMA system.

G. Image Generation

The BC-250’s Vulkan compute path also supports image generation, tested using `stable-diffusion.cpp` (`sd.cpp`) [28], which provides native Vulkan support for Stable Diffusion, FLUX, and related diffusion architectures.

All image benchmarks used a fixed seed (42), the Euler sampler, and `cfg-scale=1.0` (except SD3.5-medium: 5.0).

TABLE X
QUANTISATION IMPACT: QWEN3:8B AT TWO WEIGHT QUANTISATION LEVELS, BOTH WITH Q4_0 KV CACHE.

Quant	Gen (t/s)	Prefill (t/s)	VRAM (GiB)	Qual.
Q4_K_M	43.1	192.7	5.1	100%
Q8_0	31.2	237.2	8.5	100%

TABLE XI
IMAGE GENERATION LATENCY AT 512×512 . ALL PIPELINES USE SD.CPP/VULKAN. * RECOMMENDED.

Pipeline	Steps	Time (s)	VRAM (GiB)	Notes
SD-Turbo	4	27	2.0	Fastest; lower qual.
FLUX.2-klein-4B	4	37	6.0	Fast alt.
* klein-9B	4	67	11.8	Rec. default
Chroma Q4_0	4	67	8.4	Open-weight alt.
SD3.5-medium	28	102	6.0	High step count
FLUX.1-schnell	4	107	10.0	Previous default
FLUX.1-kontext	20	132	10.0	Image editing
FLUX.1-dev	20	167	10.0	Quality ref.

Diffusion weights were quantised to Q4_0 (FLUX.1-schnell: Q4_K; FLUX.1-dev: Q4_K_S). CLIP text encoders were offloaded to CPU (`-clip-on-cpu`) to conserve VRAM, and `-vae-tiling` was enabled at $\geq 768^2$. Ollama and the system queue runner were stopped before each session. Each configuration was run once (single warm run) with a 900 s timeout. Table XI summarises the results.

Latency scales roughly linearly with resolution: FLUX.2-klein-9B takes 67 s at 512^2 , 97 s at 768^2 , and 147 s at 1024^2 . Higher resolutions reach the 16 GiB memory wall. ESRGAN $4\times$ upscaling (tile size 192) turns 512^2 output into 2048^2 in 22 s, a practical workaround for the resolution ceiling.

Fig. 6 shows output from four pipelines given the same prompt at 512^2 .

FLUX.1-kontext-dev supports image editing: given a reference photograph and a text instruction, it produces an edited version. Fig. 7 shows an example at 512^2 in 132 s (20 steps).

H. Multimodal Vision Inference

Several models handle multimodal (image + text) input: qwen3.5:9b, gemma3:4b, and gemma3:12b. Vision inference uses Ollama’s `/api/chat` endpoint with base64-encoded images. The vision model (qwen3.5:9b) takes about 40–80 s to process a single image, depending on output length.

Fig. 8 shows a sample input and the model output. The model correctly identifies both figurines by franchise name, describes the floppy disk label text (including its orientation), and characterises the background.

I. Video Generation

Video generation was tested with the WAN 2.1 Text-to-Video 1.3B model (Q4_0) through `sd.cpp`’s Vulkan backend, using the same fixed seed (42) and CPU-offloaded text encoder as the image benchmarks. A single warm run was

(a) schnell—107 s

(b) klein-9B—67 s

(c) klein-4B—37 s

(d) Chroma—67 s

Fig. 6. Model comparison: same prompt, same resolution (512^2), four pipelines. All generated on the BC-250 via sd.cpp with Vulkan.

(a) Input photograph

(b) Kontext — 132 s

Fig. 7. Image editing with FLUX.1-kontext-dev: “turn Sonic into Shadow the Hedgehog.” 512^2 , 20 steps, Q4_0.

recorded per configuration. A 17-frame clip at 480×320 with 50 diffusion steps takes about 38 minutes: ~ 4 s for text encoding, ~ 35 minutes for diffusion (17 frames \times 50 steps on scalar-only Vulkan compute), ~ 30 s for VAE decoding, and ~ 2.5 minutes of loading overhead. The full stack (diffusion 826 MB + text encoder 3.5 GB + VAE 243 MB) fits in the 16 GiB envelope.

The larger WAN 2.2 TI2V 5B model (Q4_0, ~ 9 GB) resulted in OOM on the BC-250, so no structured results are reported for it. Output quality at 1.3B Q4_0 is recognisable but noisy; unsurprisingly, given a small, aggressively quantised model running on scalar-only hardware.

Fig. 8. Vision inference: photograph submitted to qwen3.5:9b (9.7B, Q4_K_M) with no text prompt. Description produced in ≈ 60 s (Table XII).

TABLE XII
VISION OUTPUT FROM QWEN3.5:9B FOR FIG. 8.

“This is a charming and nostalgic photo featuring two small figurines placed on a blue 3.5-inch floppy disk, which is resting on a gray outdoor table. On the left: a black hedgehog with red stripes on his head and yellow muzzle—Shadow the Hedgehog from the Sonic the Hedgehog series. On the right: a white Dalmatian puppy wearing a red firefighter helmet and a yellow collar with a red heart tag—Marshall from PAW Patrol. The floppy disk is labelled ‘2HD 1.44 MB’ and ‘INDEX’ (upside down in the image). Background: a blurred garden with green grass, bushes, and string lights with clear glass bulbs.”

VI. DISCUSSION

A. The Allocation–Utilisation Gap

As shown in Section IV-C, 128K allocation succeeds but 128K filled context times out for every model, and Ollama silently truncates some models to native limits. Any Ollama-based benchmark should verify `prompt_eval_count` to detect this.

B. Limitations

Several limitations bound what can be concluded from these results:

- 1) **Single device.** All measurements come from one BC-250 board. No comparison with other GPUs, NPUs, or cloud inference is provided.
- 2) **No standard benchmarks.** MMLU, HumanEval, GSM8K, and perplexity were not run. The quality tasks are custom and practical but not directly comparable to published suites.
- 3) **Quality task scope.** The five-task battery targets practical competence; reasoning depth and generation quality fall outside its scope.
- 4) **Vulkan only.** Results are specific to Mesa RADV Vulkan 1.4.328. Other Vulkan drivers or future Mesa versions may produce different numbers.

Fig. 9. Speed–quality trade-off across all benchmarked models. Recommended models (bold) balance speed and quality on the tested tasks.

- Software stack.** Ollama 0.18.0, kernel 6.18.9, and Mesa 25.3.4 are the tested versions; updates may shift results.
- Image/video methodology.** Image and video benchmarks use single warm runs per configuration; no statistical validation was performed for these modalities.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Benchmarking 31 LLM models on the AMD BC-250, a repurposed mining board with 16 GB unified GDDR6 and a Vulkan-only GPU, yields three principal observations.

- A Mixture-of-Experts model with 3B active parameters reaches 37.5 tok/s, exceeding the throughput of the tested 14B dense models, and at IQ2_M (≈ 2.5 bits/weight) fits 35B total parameters in 16 GB with 93% basic-task accuracy.
- Q4_0 KV cache quantisation pushes the filled-context ceiling from 16–24K to 64K with no measurable speed penalty at the tested context length.

- Context *allocation* and *utilisation* differ: 128K allocation succeeds while 128K filled times out; Ollama silently truncates some models, detectable only via `prompt_eval_count`.

The same Vulkan path also handles image generation (27–167 s at 512²), vision inference, and video generation, though these supplementary evaluations used single runs and carry less statistical weight. Repurposed UMA APUs may serve as a practical platform for edge AI workloads once the kernel memory subsystem (`ttm.pages_limit`) is properly configured.

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Data Availability: Benchmark scripts, raw result files, configuration files, and analysis code are available in the project repository [25].

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